

Research

Application of optimized generic algorithm in UAV route planning

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Abstract: The flight path planning method of UAV is studied to establish a more objective and reasonable flight path planning method that can integrate the real digital terrain. Because immune algorithm is easy to fall into the local optimum and the convergence speed is too slow, an improved immune algorithm based on Tabu criteria is proposed and applied to UAV track planning. It determines the individual evaluation criteria, crossover and high-frequency variation through gene coding, and optimizes the initial track of UAV on the digital elevation map established by the real geographical environment information, so that the track can meet various constraint conditions. Compared with the ant colony algorithm, the results show that the algorithm accelerates the convergence process and can obtain a better solution.

Keywords: UAV; Route Planning; Improved Algorithm

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1. Introduction

With the development of UAV technology, the application of UAV has changed with each passing day. In modern war and civil field, UAV has broad development space. UAV route planning refers to finding the optimal flight path from the starting point to the target point that meets the mobility performance and geographic environment information constraints of UAV under specific constraints. It is the key technology of UAV mission planning system and the technical guarantee for UAV to achieve autonomous flight. In recent years, the methods for studying track planning mainly include a-algorithm [1], artificial potential field method [2], Voronoi diagram method [3] and ant colony algorithm [4]. However, the previous route planning algorithms are often limited to 2D space or rely on the terrain information generated by mathematical methods, which is easy to make the spatial information of route planning not true and complete, and ultimately lead to the inadequacy of the planning algorithm in practical application. The algorithm proposed by a is based on the grid search space, which often leads to the large scale of the planning space and the long running time of the algorithm, which is not suitable for real-time planning. Although Szczerba and others introduced constraints into the route search process [5] and accelerated the algorithm solution process by cutting invalid nodes, it still cannot meet the demand when the planning space is too large. The artificial potential field method has a

local minimum point at the position where the attraction force and the repulsion force are equal, which easily leads to the algorithm falling into the local minimum point and stagnating, and it is often applied to 2D route planning. Voronoi diagram method is very complex in three-dimensional space route planning, and generally there is no specific feature element representation method. Compared with other algorithms, immune algorithm not only has good global search ability, but also can better prevent "premature" phenomenon, and can effectively improve the optimization speed and efficiency.

Therefore, according to the basic characteristics and target conditions of UAV route planning, the author constructs the planning space according to the real terrain elevation information and interpolates and smoothed it to meet the requirements of spatial resolution and UAV dynamic climbing conditions. The corresponding coding mode of immune algorithm, vaccine extraction and inoculation, high-frequency mutation operation and corresponding fitness function are established. The simulation experiment is carried out with MATLAB. The simulation results show that the algorithm has good time efficiency, greatly shortens the planning time, suppresses premature convergence, reduces the stagnation phenomenon when reaching the optimal solution, and can meet the requirements of off-line or on-line route planning of UAV.

2. Digital Terrain Construction

In the three-dimensional space, finding an optimal route that satisfies the constraints of UAV maneuverability is the key problem of UAV route planning. In the past, digital terrain technology often used mathematical methods to generate digital terrain [6], but the real digital terrain is changeable, and it is difficult to accurately describe it with mathematical methods. With the rapid development of digital map technology, the wide application of high-resolution digital terrain in military and civil fields has provided a broader application space for UAV route planning, especially the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) hosted by the US Department of defense and NASA.

SRTM obtains terrain information through the C-band space image radar and X-band synthetic aperture radar onboard the space shuttle Endeavour, which realizes the unification and standardization of land and ocean terrain data for the first time, and finally forms the global digital elevation model (DEM). After data preprocessing such as editing and gross error removal, the data is segmented according to geographical coordinates, and finally cut into more than 15000 maps for storage, The longitude and latitude covered by each map is $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$, its data accuracy has two formats: 1rad / s and 3rad/s, called SRTM-1 and SRTM-3, and the corresponding horizontal resolution is 30m and 90m respectively. Due to the problem of radar echo quality, srtm-3 data has a small number of empty defects and blank areas, which are mainly concentrated in the water area, high mountains and valleys with large undulations, and the elevation value is - 32768. Therefore, the empty defects should be filled before the construction of digital terrain. The author uses the interpolation method to fill the empty defects. The resolution of terrain data in Pakistan is 90m, and its accuracy cannot meet the requirements of UAV for planning space. Therefore, the author uses the two-dimensional cubic convolution interpolation method in document [7] to interpolate the terrain data. Compared with bilinear interpolation and bicubic Hermite interpolation methods, this interpolation method has higher interpolation accuracy and is continuously quadratic differentiable at the interpolation point. However, it also has disadvantages such as large calculation amount and long time-consuming. Considering such factors as complex terrain data and limited flight capability of UAV, the interpolated terrain may have areas with large slopes, which may bury hidden dangers for safe flight of UAV. It is also necessary to further smooth the slope and curvature of the terrain. After the terrain is further processed by using the terrain smoothing method in document [8], the digital terrain meets the constraint conditions of

longitudinal mobility and normal overload of UAV. Figure 1 and Figure 2 is sample image of the effect map of terrain interpolation and smoothing.

Figure 1: Sample of digital terrain interpolation and smoothing [9]

Figure 2: Sample terrain image

2. Basic Principle of Algorithm

2.1 Clonal Selection Mechanism

The selection mechanism is based on the evaluation of antibody affinity value and is used to determine how to select the antibody from the parent to be inherited into the offspring. The antibody with high affinity has more chances to be selected than the antibody with low affinity. The purpose is to avoid gene deletion, improve convergence and calculation efficiency. The author's selection mechanism is roulette selection. The relative affinity value of the antibody is denoted as $P_i = S_i / \sum S_i$. Then, according to the selection probability, the disk is divided into N parts, wherein the center angle of the i^{th} sector is $2\pi P_i$. Rotate the wheel during the selection process. If the dice fall into the i^{th} sector area, select the antibody i . the larger the area of the sector area in the wheel, the higher the antibody affinity, the greater the

probability of the dice falling into the sector, and the more chances of being selected. The author first normalized the affinity value of the antibody so that the value was between 0 and 1, so that the roulette method could be successfully used as the selection function.

2.2 Immune Memory Mechanism

When the body is subjected to external damage, the antibodies participating in the immune response are memorized and stored in the immune system. When the body is affected by the same or similar antigens again, the memory cells in the immune system can eliminate the antigens more quickly and accurately, which is called the memory function of the immune system. With reference to immune memory mechanism, clonal selection algorithm retains the few individuals with the highest affinity in the antibody population in the memory unit during each iteration, which helps to preserve the excellent characteristics of the population and accelerate the convergence speed of the algorithm.

3. Improved Immune Algorithm

Figure 3 shows the whole process flow chart of Immune Algorithm system work from starts to end.

Figure 3: Immune algorithm flow chart from start to end

3.1 Coding Design

The motion of UAV in the whole space shall be considered when UAV performs tasks. To facilitate the research, the three-dimensional space is divided into different levels by grid method, and only the motion of UAV in a single space level needs to be considered each time. The main consideration is to plan a better track on the premise of meeting the performance constraints of UAV, to minimize fuel consumption and shortest range.

The coding quality directly affects the efficiency of operators, and a good coding method can better adapt to specific problems. Combined with the characteristics of UAV route planning, the author adopts the real number string coding method, that is, each element in the string representing the antibody gene corresponds to a point coordinate (l, h). Where l denotes latitude, h denotes altitude, and the default longitude coordinates are arranged in the order of 1-N (n is the number of divided grids). Finally, the three-dimensional coordinate point representation of longitude, latitude and elevation is realized. The accuracy of the height coordinate points is 100m. According to the established digital elevation map, the code length is set as 49, and the code length is set as 2×51 to represent the UAV track. The first column of the matrix is an integer in the range of 1-51. The numerical value is decoded into latitude by the formula $Lat = 28 + 0.01 (N-1)$. Similarly, the corresponding elevation can be solved to realize the exchange of geographic information and gene coding.

The random number is used to generate the initial population, wherein the antibody coding length is the number of grids divided in space. Since some grid nodes are located below the terrain, the invalid node list is defined to store the invalid grid points. When generating the initial population, only the gene nodes of individuals in the population can join the initial population. Examples of gene coding are as follows:

3.2 Vaccine Extraction

Vaccination refers to modifying the genes or components on some gene nodes of the antibody according to the prior knowledge, so that the obtained antibody has a higher affinity with a greater probability. Due to the mobility constraints of the UAV itself, it is necessary to meet the restrictions of the maximum turning angle and the maximum climb / dive angle during the flight along the line. According to the concept of vaccine in immune algorithm, the UAV angle constraint is extracted as a vaccine, and the waypoints in the antibody that do not meet the angle constraint conditions are regenerated according to the prior knowledge.

3.3 High Frequency Variation

In the theory of immune system, the maturation and diversity of antibodies are mainly realized by the high-frequency mutation of cells, which is the difference between immune algorithm and genetic algorithm. High frequency mutation operation is to clone the corresponding number of antibody cells according to the affinity between antibody and antigen.

$$N_i = \text{Int} \left(\frac{N_c f(X_i)}{\sum_{j=1}^N f(X_j)} \right)$$

Where: N_c is the total antibody population size after cloning; $\text{Int} ()$ is a rounding function; $f(X_i)$ is the affinity value of the i th individual; N_i is the number of clones of the i th antibody. After high-frequency mutation, the antibody with high affinity generates more images, retains more excellent characteristics, and enhances the search ability of the planning space.

3.4 Taboo Criteria

The immune memory mechanism stores the individuals with high affinity in the memory set. In the process of population iteration, if the offspring has better individuals, the memory set is updated; On the contrary, the memory set remains unchanged. Although this ensures the convergence direction of the algorithm and ensures that the

population evolves to the global optimum, it also easily leads to the reduction of individual diversity and serious population degradation. Especially in the later stage of the algorithm evolution, the affinity of individuals in the population and memory set is similar or the same, and the algorithm detours at the local optimal point, which reduces the convergence efficiency of the algorithm. Therefore, the algorithm introduces the tabu criterion. The main idea of the tabu criterion is to mark the obtained local optimal solutions and avoid these local optimal solutions in the process of further iteration. Individuals whose affinity has not increased recently during the iteration are added to the taboo table. Randomly generated individuals, such as in the neighborhood formed by individuals in the taboo list, will not be introduced into the population. When the number of taboos in the taboo list exceeds the threshold, these individuals are pardoned. The amnesty criterion is to further expand the search space, enable excellent individuals to participate in the immune cycle again, and ensure the continuous search ability of antigenic space. Thus, the random individuals introduced into the population have better spatial distribution, reduce circuitous search, ensure more local best points, strengthen the global search ability of the algorithm, and accelerate the convergence speed.

4. Results and Analysis

The parameters of the improved immune algorithm are set as follows: the population size is 80; The population size is 10; The gene length was 51; The number of iterations is 900; The memory population size was 5; The probability of variation was 0.7. The parameters of ant colony algorithm are set as follows: the path value of ant colony algorithm is 10; The initial colony was set to 100 ants.

Figure 4: Ant colony algorithm for route planning

Figure 4 shows the route planning of UAV using classical ant colony algorithm. The route in the figure is frequently deflected, resulting in high cost of route and unsatisfactory route planning results.

Figure 5: Ant colony algorithm fitness change trend chart

Figure 5 is a graph showing the fitness change trend of the track planning results obtained by the ant colony algorithm. The route and fitness curve obtained by the improved immune algorithm are shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7 respectively.

Figure 6: Improved immune algorithm for route planning

Figure 7: Evolutionary fitness curve of improved algorithm

It can be seen from the observation and comparison of Figure 4 and Figure 6 that the track obtained by the ant colony algorithm is curved and undulating, and the track obtained by the improved immune algorithm is smooth and stable, and the track quality is significantly improved. It can be seen from Figure 6 that the fitness function value of the UAV has been showing a good upward trend, which reflects the good evolutionary performance of the improved immune algorithm and eliminates the oscillation phenomenon of the traditional immune algorithm in the evolution process. In contrast, the search of ant colony algorithm will be in a standstill, and the global search ability is weak.

Table 1: Comparison of improved algorithm and ant colony algorithm

Algorithm	Improved Algorithm		Ant Colony	
	Range	Time	Range	Time
<i>i</i> th Time				
1	69.659	20.68	120.452	116.88
2	54.451	20.38	120.659	86.38
3	48.761	23.69	135.489	98.29

The performance of the improved immune algorithm is significantly better than that of ant colony algorithm. Table 1 is a comparison table of the three operation results of the improved immune algorithm and the ant colony algorithm. It can be found that the improved immune algorithm is significantly better than the ant colony algorithm in terms of both range cost and time consumption.

5. Conclusion

Aiming at the problems that the geographic information model is not intuitive and real enough during UAV route planning, and the accuracy of route planning algorithm is not high, an improved immune algorithm based on digital

map is proposed. The introduction of digital terrain makes the research foundation of UAV route planning more practical. The improvement of the immune algorithm also makes up for the shortcomings of the traditional immune algorithm, such as slow convergence speed and low optimization accuracy. Taking advantage of the excellent characteristics of the immune algorithm, it proposes to use the prior knowledge to guide the evolution direction of the algorithm, and uses the tabu criteria in the tabu search algorithm to reduce the number of iterative searches of the algorithm, speed up the convergence speed of the algorithm, The experimental results show that the improved immune algorithm not only has excellent search performance and less time consumption, but also has high optimization accuracy, smooth and stable path, and the route planning can meet the kinematic constraints of UAV. At the same time, this method has a good generalization significance in solving similar path planning problems.

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